

ISic3659

I.Sicily inscription 3659

Language

Latin

Type

graffiti

Material

stone

Object

wall;

tabula ansata

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

excavation spring 1916, via Vittorio Emanuele, east of Duomo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR072804

1. XVII K(alendas) Septemb(res)
2. Feridius Cereris dominae [s(ervus)]
3. hic sibi suabiter suaviter fec(it) e [o]
4. rum tres adulescentes
5. quorum nomina lege
6. Onesimus et L(ucius) Valerius
7. Cas(s)ianus et Filumenus
8. unus cum mulierae muliere ea
9. Taurus multis annis habe have facian(t)
10. co(n)iu(n)ximus
11. propitiam.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 072804

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1919.0057

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 58-60 fig.7

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